

LEVEL OF AWARENESS AND EXTENT OF INTEGRATION OF DISASTER RISK REDUCTION IN SCHOOL PRACTICES

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the level of awareness and extent of integration of disaster risk reduction and management (DRRM) in teaching among 43 teachers of Northville 15 Integrated School, District 4, Division of Angeles City, during the school year 2023–2024, using a quantitative-descriptive research design. The findings revealed that teachers were “moderately aware” of DRRM, particularly in disaster-related knowledge, preparedness, adaptation, awareness, and risk perception. The integration of DRRM into education was to a “moderate extent,” focusing on attitude, action, school policy, preparedness planning, and resource mobilization. Problems encountered included lack of training, limited resources, and absence of specific training materials, which were identified as “highly serious” and “very serious” concerns. Based on these findings, a school disaster risk reduction and management plan was proposed, emphasizing hazard awareness, preparedness, and roles before, during, and after disasters. Recommendations included implementing the proposed plan, enhancing school-based DRRM programs with stakeholder participation, conducting regular evaluations of DRRM activities, fostering linkages with government agencies, and increasing disaster preparedness drills. Further research was encouraged to enhance disaster management knowledge and skills.

Keywords: *Disaster Risk Reduction, Awareness of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management*

INTRODUCTION

Disaster is a major disruption that happens over a relatively short period that affects the community or a society. Over the past thirty years, natural disasters' rate of recurrence and impact has increased and economic damages have tripled globally (Sutton as cited by Medrano, 2023). Typhoons, earthquakes, volcanic eruptions, and floods cause loss of life and property destruction and damaged many people, including the government. Many dangerous events and disasters escalate into crises and emergencies, resulting in mass casualties due to lack of training and preparedness for these disasters.

Disasters have always been a result of human interaction with nature, technology and other living entities. Sometimes unpredictable and sudden, sometimes slow and lingering, various types of disasters continually affect daily lives. Human beings as innovative creatures have sought new ways in which to curb the devastating effects of disasters.

However, for years human conduct regarding disasters has been reactive in nature. Communities, sometimes aware of the risks that they face, would wait in anticipation of a disastrous event and then activate plans and procedures. Human social and economic development has further contributed to creating vulnerability and thus weakening the ability of humans to cope with disasters and their effects. Disasters impede human development. Gains in development are inextricably linked to the level of exposure to disaster risk within any given community. In the same light, the level of disaster risk prevalent in a community is linked to the developmental choices exerted by that community. The link between disasters and development is well researched and documented. The fact that disasters impact on development (e.g. a school being washed away in a flood) and development increases or decreases the risk of disasters (e.g. introducing earthquake-resistant building techniques) is widely accepted (Granstrom, 2022).

Natural calamities come in the most unexpected moments of people's lives. Its impact is felt everywhere for it hits all areas worldwide in different intensities and in various forms. The global community is experiencing an increasing number of disasters that range in all forms of great devastation (Soriano, 2019). Earthquakes, tsunami, typhoon and flood in many countries around the globe are recorded in the history of natural calamities for they create serious threat to the community. Disaster education, including studies on disaster risks, mitigation and readiness strategies, is one approach to reducing the negative consequences of disasters (Toyado, 2022).

Not only are these events increasing in frequency, but they are also growing in magnitude, due to the worsening effects of climate change, leading to more climate disasters that severely disrupt the functioning of daily life. Therefore, it is important to study climate disasters such as tropical cyclones, also known as typhoons, droughts, heat

waves, and flooding, amongst others, in order to understand how to cope with and stay resilient to its effects.

The Philippines is a disaster-prone country because of its geographical location. The archipelago is located in the Pacific Ring of Fire, making it prone to geological natural disasters such as volcanic eruptions and earthquakes. The location of the Philippines is also highly susceptible to various meteorological hazards. The country is located in the path of tropical cyclones that can be categorized as tropical depression, tropical storm, severe tropical storm, typhoon, and super typhoon (Mamon as cited by Cabuga and Cañete, 2023).

Since the country is categorically developing, these disasters have been known as issues that deter progress due to their long-term effects. To respond to the outcome of calamity disasters, the government and schools intend to do action about readiness to reduce the destruction, establishing a more concrete management plan that constitutes prevention and action to carry out preparedness.

Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) is an approach to systematically identify, assess and reduce that risk. Specifically, the purpose of DRR is to minimize vulnerabilities and disaster risks throughout society to avoid or lessen the adverse impacts of natural hazards, as well as, to facilitate sustainable development. The Department of Education always advocates the disaster drill on Disaster Risk Reduction in the field, to heighten the level of awareness of school administrators, teachers, pupils, and stakeholders (Peneciba, 2020).

According to Cruz (2022), schools are universal institution for sharing knowledge and skills, schools are expected to be role models in disaster prevention. Successful disaster mitigation is one of the ultimate tests of the success of the education provided over generations. With this, Disaster Risk Reduction is being implemented in the school system to keep the environment for children and their families safe during the emergencies. Natural calamities can hamper and devastate the learning process of learners; it may be formal or informal.

In disasters or emergencies, the vulnerability of school-aged children to risks like illness and trauma is prevalent. They require special care and attention of schools and stakeholders who need to offer safety and shelter to these children displaced by disasters. Prevention, mitigation, preparedness, response, and rehabilitation are primary procedures that a school and its stakeholders may employ before, during and after the occurrence of a disaster to protect and preserve school children (Abejuela, 2021).

These disasters, whether natural, bio-hazard or man-made, have particularly affected school communities with students, teachers and school staff also among those injured, displaced or killed. Schools often serve as evacuation centers which further contribute to the disruption of classes. To reduce disaster-related risks and to mitigate their effects, there is an urgent need to integrate and promote disaster risk management initiatives.

Existing risk reduction and risk management measures need to be assessed to find out if these are adequate to promote hazard/disaster awareness, manage impacts, and help all school communities reduce the risk of threats from natural and man-made or induced disasters or address the gaps in their implementation.

Risk management includes identifying health and safety hazards, determining the probability of their occurrence, estimating their potential impacts to the schools and the communities at risk, enumerating and implementing the risk reduction measures like hazard mapping, vulnerability analysis, potential losses estimation, and strategic disaster prevention/mitigation development.

Governments all over the globe implement DRR, which is an organized and step-by-step approach to identify, assess and reduce the risks inflicted by disasters. It is an integral effort in managing disasters by strengthening the capacities of communities toward the risks and adverse impacts of natural hazards. The Philippines is one of the countries who agreed on the implementation.

The academe can make or unmake the lives of people as well as certain situations in the community. This great responsibility is a big challenge on the educational sector on how they can become agents of change in society specifically on environmental issues. The basic issues are environmental education, values integration and disaster mitigation. The best hope for learning to live sustainably lies in the schooling that is smart by nature. It includes experiencing the natural world; learning how nature sustains life; nurturing healthy communities; recognizing the implications of the ways people feed and provision themselves; and knowing well the places where they live, work and learn. Teachers are in a prime position to be able to weave these basics throughout the curriculum at every grade level (Center for Ecoliteracy as cited by Manuel and Gelido, 2021).

Disaster Risk Reduction must be inculcated in education since everyone can be affected by it. Awareness will make students be resilient to disaster. Antonio (2017) opined that undertaking preparedness and building awareness towards disaster risks is the first step of today's disaster management. According to Delorino (2019), awareness on the components of Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) can help lessen the impacts of incoming disasters.

Thus, this study assessed the level of preparedness of the teachers on disaster risk reduction in Northville 15 Integrated School, District 4, Division of Angeles City during school year 2023-2024.

Research Questions

This study assessed the level of awareness of teachers on disaster risk reduction management and extent of integration of disaster risk reduction in teaching in Northville 15 Integrated School, District 4, Division of Angeles City during the school year 2023-2024.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following sub-problems:

1. How is the level of awareness of disaster risk reduction and management of the teachers described in terms of the following:
 - 1.1 Disaster-related knowledge;
 - 1.2 Disaster preparedness and readiness;
 - 1.3 Disaster adaptation;
 - 1.4 Disaster awareness, and;
 - 1.5 Disaster risk perception?
2. What is the extent of integration in education of disaster risk reduction and management in terms of the following:
 - 2.1 Attitude and action;
 - 2.2 School policy;
 - 2.3 Preparedness and planning; and
 - 2.4 Resource mobilization?
3. What are the problems met by the teachers in the integration of disaster risk reduction in school practices?
4. What school disaster risk reduction and management plan can be proposed to enhance the knowledge and preparedness on disaster?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study assessed the level of awareness among teachers and extent of integration of disaster risk reduction and management in teaching in Northville 15 Integrated School, District 4, Division of Angeles City during the school year 2023-2024 through the quantitative-descriptive research design.

Through the quantitative-descriptive research design, this study determined the level of awareness of disaster risk reduction issues of the teachers in terms of disaster-related knowledge, disaster preparedness and readiness, disaster adaptation, disaster awareness, and disaster risk perception. It was also used to assess the extent of integration of disaster risk reduction in education in terms of attitude and action, school policy, preparedness planning and resource mobilization. Further, it was utilized to look into the problems met by teachers in the integration of disaster risk reduction in teaching.

Based on the findings, a school disaster management plan was proposed to enhance the knowledge and preparedness on disaster.

Sources of Data

This study was conducted in Northville 15 Integrated School, District 4, Division of Angeles City during the school year 2023-2024 with 43 teachers as respondents of the study. They provided information to answer the sub-problems raised in the study.

Instrumentation and Data Collection

The main data gathering instrument in this study was a constructed questionnaire that consists of three parts. Part I dealt on the level of awareness of disaster risk reduction issues; Part II focused on the extent of integration of disaster risk reduction in education; and Part III looked into the problems met in the integration of disaster risk reduction. Upon completion of the questionnaire, it was presented to the researcher's adviser. Suggestions were incorporated to improve the instrument.

The researcher personally administered the questionnaires for easy retrieval. The responses were tabulated and interpreted based on appropriate statistical tools.

Tool for Data Analysis

Weighted Mean was used to answer sub-problem numbers 1, 2 and 3.

The formula is:

$$WM = \frac{\sum fx}{N}$$

Where:

WM = Weighted Mean

$\sum fx$ = the sum of the average weighted mean

N = the number of cases

Data gathered were interpreted by using the following references:

Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)		
		Sub-problem No. 1	Sub-problem No. 2	Sub-problem No. 3
5	4.50-5.00	Fully Aware (FA)	Full Extent (FE)	Highly Serious (HS)
4	3.50-4.49	Very Much Aware (VMA)	Great Extent (GE)	Very Serious (VS)
3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Aware (MA)	Moderate Extent (ME)	Moderately Serious (MS)
2	1.50-2.49	Slightly Aware (SA)	Slight Extent (SE)	Slightly Serious (SS)
1	1.00-1.49	Not Aware (NA)	Not At All (NAA)	Not a Problem (NP)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the results of data gathered and the discussion of the interpretation of data.

Level of Awareness of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management

This section presents the level of awareness of disaster risk reduction and management of the teachers in Northville 15 Integrated School, District 4, Division of Angeles City to answer sub-problem number 1. The level of awareness is described in terms of disaster-related knowledge, disaster preparedness and readiness, disaster adaptation, disaster awareness, and disaster risk perception.

The data are presented in Tables 1A, 1B, 1C, 1D and 1E.

Disaster-Related Knowledge

Disaster-related knowledge is the comprehensive information in all the dimensions of disaster risk, including hazards, exposure, vulnerability, organizations and countries, and their assets.

Table 1A shows the level of awareness of the teachers in terms of disaster-related knowledge.

TABLE 1A
Level of Awareness of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management in Terms of Disaster-Related Knowledge

Indicators	WM	DE
• I know when a disaster will happen.	4.00	VMA
• I know there is no prevention for the occurrence of disaster.	3.81	VMA
• I have been a participant in a disaster risk education seminar and training.	3.00	MA
OVERALL WM	3.60	VMA
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Fully Aware (FA)
4	3.50-4.49	Very Much Aware (VMA)
3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Aware (MA)
2	1.50-2.49	Slightly Aware (SA)
1	1.00-1.49	Not Aware (NA)

As shown in Table 1A, the teachers are “very much aware” when disaster will happen and that there is no prevention for the occurrence of disaster for WM of 4.00 and 3.81, respectively. However, they are “moderately aware” of participation in a disaster risk education seminar and training for WM of 3.00. Overall, they are “very much aware” and have knowledge on disaster.

These results imply that although the teachers have knowledge on disaster and its prevention, they lack understanding on the importance of participating in a disaster risk education seminar and training.

Disaster Preparedness and Readiness

Table 1B shows the level of awareness of the teachers in terms of disaster preparedness and readiness.

TABLE 1B
Level of Awareness of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management in Terms of Disaster Preparedness and Readiness

Indicators	WM	DE																		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I know the significance of sharing knowledge and experiences of disaster. 	4.81	FA																		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I recognize the importance of making conversations about disasters with family members, neighbors, relatives, friends, and colleagues. 	4.65	FA																		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I know the government is ready to provide assistance after disaster 	4.00	VMA																		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I am confident that reconstruction activities can be implemented after disaster. 	3.83	VMA																		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I gain enough knowledge about disasters from experts who work or conduct activities for disaster reduction and management. 	4.05	VMA																		
OVERALL WM	4.27	VMA																		
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean <table style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 33%;">Point Values</td> <td style="width: 33%;">Statistical Limits</td> <td style="width: 33%;">Descriptive Equivalent (DE)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>4.50-5.00</td> <td>Fully Aware (FA)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>3.50-4.49</td> <td>Very Much Aware (VMA)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>2.50-3.49</td> <td>Moderately Aware (MA)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>1.50-2.49</td> <td>Slightly Aware (SA)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>1.00-1.49</td> <td>Not Aware (NA)</td> </tr> </table>			Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)	5	4.50-5.00	Fully Aware (FA)	4	3.50-4.49	Very Much Aware (VMA)	3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Aware (MA)	2	1.50-2.49	Slightly Aware (SA)	1	1.00-1.49	Not Aware (NA)
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2	1.50-2.49	Slightly Aware (SA)																		
1	1.00-1.49	Not Aware (NA)																		

As presented in Table 1B, the teachers find it significant to share knowledge and experiences of disasters and recognize the importance of making conversations about

disasters with their family and other people as evidenced by the WM of 4.81 and 4.65, respectively, both “fully aware.” They are “very much aware” that the government can give assistance during disasters, are confident there will be immediate rehabilitation after a disaster and gain knowledge from experts of disaster risks with WM of 4.00, 3.83 and 4.05, respectively.

These results imply that the teachers are aware, ready and prepared on disaster risks.

Disaster Adaptation

Table 1C presents the level of awareness of the teachers in terms of disaster adaptation.

TABLE 1C
Level of Awareness of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management in Terms of Disaster Adaptation

Indicators	WM	DE
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I am aware of the shelter areas or evacuation centers, and open spaces in case of a disaster. 	4.10	VMA
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I am aware about which government institution needs to be coordinated and contacted with after disaster. 	3.00	MA
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I am informed about disaster prone area. 	3.15	MA
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I obtained sufficient information about disaster adaptation from the local government or from NGSs. 	3.21	MA
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I am fully aware and informed about the evacuation system and plan in my locality or area. 	2.00	SA
OVERALL WM	3.09	MA
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Fully Aware (FA)
4	3.50-4.49	Very Much Aware (VMA)
3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Aware (MA)
2	1.50-2.49	Slightly Aware (SA)
1	1.00-1.49	Not Aware (NA)

As presented in Table 1C, the teachers are “very much aware” of the shelter areas or evacuation centers and open spaces in case of disaster (WM=4.10). They are “moderately aware” that government institutions can give assistance during disaster, on accident prone areas and sufficient information on disaster adaptation implemented by local government units and non-governmental organizations with WM of 3.00, 3.15 and 3.21, respectively. However, they are “slightly aware” about the evacuation system and plan of their locality.

Although the teachers are aware of disaster adaptation, there is a need for information dissemination on evacuation system in their locality.

Disaster Awareness

Table 1D presents the level of awareness of the teachers in terms of disaster awareness.

TABLE 1D
Level of Awareness of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management in Terms of Disaster Awareness

Indicators	WM	DE																		
• I actively participate for disaster awareness campaign.	4.10	VMA																		
• I am prepared with emergency kits and bags in case of disaster.	2.00	SA																		
• I prioritize awareness in the local, regional and national level.	4.05	VMA																		
• I am aware on the importance of building or infrastructure retrofitting.	1.40	NA																		
OVERALL WM	2.89	MA																		
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean <table style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="text-align: left;">Point Values</th> <th style="text-align: left;">Statistical Limits</th> <th style="text-align: left;">Descriptive Equivalent (DE)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>4.50-5.00</td> <td>Fully Prepared (FP)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>3.50-4.49</td> <td>Very Much Prepared (VMP)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>2.50-3.49</td> <td>Moderately Prepared (MP)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>1.50-2.49</td> <td>Slightly Prepared (SP)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>1.00-1.49</td> <td>Not Prepared (NP)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)	5	4.50-5.00	Fully Prepared (FP)	4	3.50-4.49	Very Much Prepared (VMP)	3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Prepared (MP)	2	1.50-2.49	Slightly Prepared (SP)	1	1.00-1.49	Not Prepared (NP)
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)																		
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3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Prepared (MP)																		
2	1.50-2.49	Slightly Prepared (SP)																		
1	1.00-1.49	Not Prepared (NP)																		

Table 1D shows that the teachers are “very much aware” on disaster risk reduction at local, regional and national level because of various disaster awareness campaign with WM of 4.10 and 4.05, respectively. However, they are “slightly aware” on the importance of preparing emergency kits and bags in case of emergency (WM=2.00) and “not aware” of the importance of building or infrastructure retrofitting (WM=1.40). These imply that building or infrastructure retrofitting should be disseminated appropriately as the teachers are not aware of it at all.

Disaster Risk Perception

Table 1E presents the level of awareness of the teachers in terms of disaster risk perception.

TABLE 1E
Level of Awareness of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management in Terms of Disaster Risk Perception

Indicators	WM	DE
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I am sure that large-scale disasters will definitely happen in the next 10 years. • I think my locality is safe from all types of disasters. • I think my house/building is well designed to withstand an earthquake. 	2.00 2.10 3.21	SA SA MA
OVERALL WM	2.44	SA
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Fully Aware (FA)
4	3.50-4.49	Very Much Aware (VMA)
3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Aware (MA)
2	1.50-2.49	Slightly Aware (SA)
1	1.00-1.49	Not Aware (NA)

As presented in Table 1E, the teachers are “slightly aware” that large-scale disasters will definitely happen in the next 10 years and that their localities or areas are safe from all types of disasters with WM of 2.00 and 2.10, respectively. They are “moderately aware” that their house can withstand an earthquake (WM=3.21).

These imply that although they may have knowledge on disaster risk education, the teachers are not knowledgeable about earthquake resistant structures as regard their houses and other buildings.

SUMMARY TABLE

Indicators	WM	DE
• Disaster-related knowledge	3.60	VMA
• Disaster preparedness and readiness	4.27	VMA
• Disaster adaptation	3.09	MA
• Disaster awareness	2.89	MA
• Disaster risk perception	2.44	SA
OVERALL WM	3.26	MA

Based on the Summary Table, the teachers of Northville 15 Integrated School are “moderately aware” of disaster risk reduction and management as shown by the overall WM of 3.26. Some aspects of disaster risks are understood by the teachers and most of

them are ready, adapted and prepared on the hazards that natural disasters can cause. However, they have low disaster risk perception. For them to have an effective and protective response and action toward imminent dangers of natural hazards, risk perception among the teachers should be developed.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Generally, the teachers are moderately aware of disaster risk reduction and management which indicates they have knowledge of disaster risk reduction and management within reasonable limits.
 2. Generally, the teachers integrate disaster risk reduction and management in their teaching to a moderate extent; they apply knowledge in the integration of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management to education with less intensity.
 3. Problems met by the teachers in the integration of disaster risk reduction and management in school practices include the lack of training among the teachers, limited resources and no specific training materials for disaster risk reduction management.
 4. The proposed school disaster risk reduction and management plan focused on hazard, risk and vulnerability, preparedness, and roles and responsibilities of persons involved before, during and after the disaster.
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Recommendations

On the basis of the findings and conclusions drawn, the following recommendations were offered:

1. The proposed school disaster risk reduction and management plan should be considered for implementation to enhance the knowledge and preparedness on disaster.
2. School-based disaster risk reduction and management program should be participated by various stakeholders all year round to insure a continuous improvement of disaster management strategies and policies for the people to internalize and can act instantly as their own initiative during emergency situations.
3. All implemented Disaster Risk Reduction Management programs and activities should have a regular or annual evaluation to study needed improvements to attain full implementation for all parameters.
4. Linkages with other government agencies should be encouraged for training and upgrading of facilities needed.
5. The disaster preparedness activities of the school should be enhanced through more frequent drills to match the implementation of risk reduction management.
6. Further studies about disaster risk reduction and management are encouraged among future researchers in order to improve and broaden disaster management knowledge and skills.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author hereby declare that this study was conducted in full compliance with ethical research standards. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents prior to their participation, ensuring that they were fully aware of the study's purpose, procedures, and potential implications. Respondents were given the freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without any repercussions. Anonymity was maintained throughout the research process to protect the respondents' identities, and their well-being was prioritized and safeguarded at all times. The authors affirm that no conflict of interest existed in the conduct of this study. Strict measures were taken to avoid plagiarism, ensuring originality and integrity in all aspects of the research. Furthermore, no bias was introduced in the interpretation of the findings, and the results were utilized solely for academic and research purposes.

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